

Drop Hand as A Rare Complication of Anterior Glenohumeral Dislocation: A Case Report of Radial Nerve Palsy

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ABSTRACT

Background: Anterior shoulder dislocation is the most common type of glenohumeral dislocation, often associated with soft tissue injury, one of them is neurologic deficit.

Objectives: Radial nerve palsy following glenohumeral dislocation without associated fracture is a rare complication that can lead to significant functional impairment, such as drop hand that characterized by the inability to extend the wrist and fingers. Glenohumeral dislocation with drop hand will severely impair hand function and the ability to perform activities of daily living.

Aim: To assess the effectiveness of rehabilitation program in improving ROM, muscle strength and recovery of radial nerve function in a patient following a shoulder dislocation.

Methods: This case report discusses a 36-year-old female patient who developed radial nerve palsy after an anterior dislocation of the right glenohumeral joint due to a motorcycle accident. The patient presented with shoulder pain, inability to extension the wrist and fingers, and occasional tingling sensation in the dorsal right hand. Initial radiographs confirmed anterior dislocation of the right glenohumeral joint without associated fracture and the patient underwent open reduction and internal fixation (ORIF) with pinning. Postoperatively, wrist and thumb extension remained impaired, and rehabilitation program was initiated including ultrasound diathermy, gradual range of motion exercise and muscle strengthening for right shoulder, electrical stimulation, stretching and passive range of motion on extensor group of wrist and finger muscles and give wrist splint.

Result: The results of the serial examinations over a four month period showed gradual improvement in ROM and MMT grade.

Conclusion: Postoperative medical rehabilitation therapy plays a crucial role in enhancing muscle strength and promoting recovery in patients radial nerve palsy with shoulder dislocation and still need to continue until full recovery.

KEYWORDS: drop hand, radial nerve palsy, anterior shoulder dislocation, rehabilitation

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INTRODUCTION

The radial nerve, originating from the posterior cord of the brachial plexus, innervates the extensor muscles of the upper limb and supplies sensory input to the posterior arm, forearm, and hand¹. Radial nerve palsy following glenohumeral dislocation without associated fracture is a rare complication that can lead to significant functional impairment, such as drop hand that characterized by the inability to extend the wrist and fingers. Glenohumeral dislocation with drop hand will severely impair hand function and the ability to perform

activities of daily living². Due to its long and complex anatomical pathway, especially around the humeral shaft and spiral groove, it is susceptible to injury from trauma, compression, and surgical complications³. Radial nerve palsy is clinically marked by wrist drop, inability to extend the fingers and thumb, and sensory loss in the anatomical snuffbox. The aim of rehabilitation in the treatment of shoulder dislocation is to restore pain-free and normal motor control of the affected shoulder⁴. The implementation of ultrasound diathermy, electrical stimulation, gradual range of

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motion exercise and muscle strengthening has been demonstrated to be an effective intervention. The rationale behind this case report is the rarity of drop hand of anterior glenohumeral dislocation. Moreover, there is a paucity of literature regarding the medical rehabilitation of patients with drop hands of anterior glenohumeral dislocation. The objective of this case report is to provide a comprehensive description of the medical rehabilitation process for patients who have experienced drop hand of anterior glenohumeral dislocation, with a focus on its development.

CASE REPORT

A 36-year-old female came to Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation department presented with complaints of pain

in the right shoulder and an inability to lift her right wrist and fingers since 1 month ago, occasionally accompanied by tingling sensations. This complaint arises after the patient has experienced of motorcycle accidents, she fell on her right side and struck her right shoulder against the asphalt, she was brought to Wangaya Hospital then underwent open reduction and internal fixation (ORIF) with pinning, with radiographic findings indicating an anterior dislocation of the right glenohumeral joint. The patient had no prior medical history and was not taking any regular medications.

Figure 1. Radiographic Imaging AP/Lateral

Figure 2. Postoperative X-ray Right Shoulder, AP view

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Based on the physical examination findings from inspection the patient was using an arm sling, a cock-up splint with an elastic bandage and a “drop hand” deformity was present. Shoulder range of motion (ROM) could not be assessed due to pin fixation. Right elbow ROM was measured at 30°–120°. Manual Muscle Testing (MMT) score for muscles innervated by radial nerve were as follows: triceps, brachioradialis and supinator 3 (due to pain). MMT score for extensor carpi

radialis longus and brevis, extensor carpi ulnaris, extensor digitorum communis, extensor digiti minimi, abductor pollicis longus, extensor pollicis longus & brevis and extensor indicis all were 0. Sensory examination using light touch revealed a 50% sensory deficit in the distribution of the radial nerve. Patient was diagnosed right drop hand due to radial nerve palsy and post-ORIF pinning due to glenohumeral with stiffness right shoulder and elbow.

Figure 3. Clinical patient with drop hand

Figure 4. Anterior view

The rehabilitation plan included physiotherapy three times per week consisting of electrical stimulation of extensor group of wrist and fingers, gentle stretching elbow, passive ROM wrist and fingers to extension position, no ROM

exercise for right shoulder until pin removal. The patient is asked to continue using the cock up splint from the casting. Additionally, the patient is advised to switch to a lighter and easier to use wrist splint.

Figure 5. Clinical patient with wrist splint

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On February 27, 2025, by the time after wound healing on the site of ORIF pinning and there was no sign of inflammation, we added ultrasound diathermy therapy for right shoulder, gradual range of motion exercise and muscle strengthening for right shoulder, electrical stimulation for wrist and fingers extensor group muscle, passive ROM extension wrist and fingers.

On May 8, 2025, the shoulder ROM was assessed for the first time, with the following findings: passive flexion 0-135°, active flexion 0-60°, passive abduction 0-135°, and active abduction 0-45°. MMT of the shoulder demonstrated improvement from grade 2 to 3. Elbow ROM was improved until full range of motion (0 to full). Additionally, there was noted improvement in MMT of the wrist extensor from grade 1 to 2, and of the thumb and fingers extensors from grade 0 to 1.

On June 19, 2025, an improvement in shoulder flexion ROM was observed, with passive flexion measured at 0-165° and active flexion 0-90°. MMT of the shoulder demonstrated

progression from grade 3 to 4. There's no clinical signs of drop hand were observed followed by improvement in MMT of the wrist extensors increased from grade 2 to 3, MMT thumb and fingers extensor showed improvement from grade 1 to 2. MMT of other muscles innervated by the radial nerve including the triceps, brachioradialis, and supinator also improved from grade 3 to 4.

On July 18, 2025, an improvement passive flexion reaching 0-full, active flexion 0-120°, and active abduction 0-90° in shoulder. There was also an increase in MMT of the thumb abductor and fingers extensor from grade 2 to 3 and sensory deficit decrease 25% was observe in the distribution of the radial nerve. But, MMT thumb extensor and extensor indicis remained to. Physiotherapy continued three times weekly with ultrasound diathermy, active range of motion exercise and muscle strengthening for right shoulder, electrical stimulation, active range of motion on extensor group of wrist and finger muscles.

Table 1. Follow up physical assessment

Follow up	I	II	III	V	VI
	21/03/25	04/04/25	08/05/25	19/06/25	18/07/25
ROM Shoulder D	cannot be evaluated	cannot be evaluated	passive flexion 0-135 active flexion 0-60 passive abduction 0-135 active abduction 0-45	passive flexion 0-165 active flexion 0-90 passive abduction 0-135 active abduction 0-45	passive flexion 0-full active flexion 0-120 passive abduction 0-135 active abduction 0-90
ROM Elbow D	flexion 30-120	flexion 30-120	0-full	0-full	0-full
Drop Hand	+	+	+	-	-
MMT Shoulder	2	2	3	4	4
MMT Triceps D	3	3	3	4	4
MMT Brachioradialis D	3	3	3	4	4
MMT Wrist Extensor D	0	1	2	3	3
MMT Supinator D	3	3	3	4	4
MMT Extensor Digitorum Communis D	0	0	1	2	3
MMT Digiti Minimi D	0	0	1	2	3
MMT Abductor pollicis longus D	0	0	1	2	3
MMT Extensor thumb D	0	0	0	1	2
MMT Extensor Indicis Proprius D	0	0	0	1	2

The last radiographic imaging of the right shoulder (AP view) taken on May 20, 2025, showed evidence of calcification around the right humeral neck, suggestive of calcified tendinitis.

Figure 6. Radiographic imaging, AP view

Figure 7. Clinical patient after 4 months rehabilitation program (Lateral View)

DISCUSSION

Shoulder dislocations, particularly anterior types, are the most frequently dislocated large joints, with a reported incidence of 24 per 100,000 person-years⁶. Anterior shoulder dislocation is associated with nerve injuries with an incidence ranging from 3 to 21% based on clinical diagnosis⁷. While the axillary nerve is the most commonly affected nerve in such cases, isolated radial nerve injuries, though rare, particularly in the absence of an associated fracture. When it does occur, it can lead to significant functional impairment, including wrist drop and inability to extend the fingers and thumb⁸.

Radial nerve palsy may manifest at various anatomical levels from the axilla to the forearm each with distinct motor and sensory deficits. Most notably, patients present with wrist drop, reduced finger extension, and sensory loss on the dorsal aspect of the hand and fingers. Early diagnosis is essential, with EMG studies recommended between the first and third week post-injury to differentiate between neuropraxia,

axonotmesis, and neurotmesis⁹. Physical examination, including sensory testing and muscle strength grading, supports localization and severity assessment.

Treatment of radial nerve palsy depends on the severity and cause. Neuropraxia often resolves with conservative management, including splinting, physical rehabilitation, and occupational rehabilitation¹. Surgical intervention is indicated in cases of persistent motor loss or neurotmesis. Internal neurolysis and nerve grafting especially using short sural nerve grafts have demonstrated favorable outcomes, with studies reporting neurological recovery rates exceeding 80%⁹. Surgical timing, nerve gap length, and presence of scarring or associated injuries influence prognosis.

The initial physical examination findings of wrist and finger extensor weakness (MMT 0/5) and sensory deficits on the dorsum of the hand supported the diagnosis of radial nerve palsy. Radiographic evaluation confirmed the anterior shoulder dislocation without fracture. Post-operative

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management included open reduction and internal fixation (ORIF) with pinning, a procedure often necessary to restore anatomical alignment and prevent recurrent dislocation.

Over the course of four months, the patient demonstrated gradual and measurable improvement in muscle strength and joint range of motion. MMT scores for wrist extensor, thumb abduction, extensor digitorum communis and extensor digitorum minimi improved from grade 0 to 3. Similarly, shoulder flexion increased from cannot be assessed to passive flexion 0-full and elbow ROM fully normalized. MMT shoulder improved from grade 2 to 4. These findings highlight the positive impact of consistent physiotherapy interventions.

Despite persistent signs of drop hand by the fourth month, the overall improvement in muscle strength and ROM signifies meaningful neurologic and functional recovery. The presence of calcified tendinitis observed on the May 2025 radiograph may have contributed to shoulder stiffness and should be monitored in the long term. Although the patient has shown significant improvement, the radial nerve lesion has not yet fully recovered, as evidenced by the inability to perform thumb extension and index finger extension. Therefore, the patient is advised to continue the rehabilitation program to increase the probability of further recovery of the radial nerve lesion.

CONCLUSION

Radial nerve palsy following anterior shoulder dislocation without fracture is a rare but disabling complication. Early diagnosis, multidisciplinary management, and continuity of care through medical rehabilitation are essential for optimal outcomes. In this case, postoperative medical rehabilitation therapy plays a crucial role in enhancing muscle strength and promoting recovery in patients with radial nerve palsy following shoulder dislocation and still need to continue until full recovery.

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